

FEATURES OF SYSTEM OF MANAGEMENT OF HIGHER PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION IN A CONTEXT OF INNOVATIVE PROCESS OF AN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotation. The article presents an analysis of the management system of a higher professional educational institution in the context of the innovation process of the education system. The article considers a range of management problems that are fundamentally new and relevant for the practical reform of the educational system. These include new values and goals of management, innovations in university management, methodology and technology of development programs, etc.

Keywords: management systems, innovation process, competitiveness of the University, external and internal environment of the functioning of the system of higher professional education, multilevel, management subsystems.

Аннотация. В статье представлен анализ системы менеджмента высшего профессионального учебного заведения в контексте инновационного процесса системы образования. Рассматривается круг управленческих проблем, отличающихся принципиальной новизной и актуальностью для практического реформирования образовательной системы. В их числе новые ценности и цели управления, нововведения в ВУЗовском управлении, методология и технология разработки программ развития и т.д.

Ключевые слова: системы менеджмента, инновационный процесс, конкурентоспособность ВУЗа, внешняя и внутренняя среда функционирования системы высшего профессионального образования, многоуровневость, подсистемы управления.

Аннотация. Мақолада контекстда олий касбий таълим муассасасини бошқариш тизимининг таҳлили келтирилган таълим тизимининг инновацион жараёни. Мақолада бир қатор кўриб чиқилади тубдан янги бўлган бошқарув муаммолари ва таълимни амалий ислоҳ қилиш учун тегишли тизим. Буларга менежментнинг янги қадриятлари ва мақсадлари, инновациялар қиради университет менежментида, ривожланиш дастурларининг методологияси ва технологияси ва бошқалар.

Калит сўзлар: менежмент тизимлари, инновацион жараён, университетнинг рақобатбардошлиги, олий касбий таълим тизими фаолиятининг ташиқи ва ички муҳити, кўп, бошқарув қўйи тизимлари.

Profound socio-economic transformations in Kazakhstan and the transition to a market economy pose the most important pedagogical problem of improvin the educational management system for Kazakhstan education. Currently, educational institutions are forced to engage in various forms of self-financing activities to solve their tasks.

Innovative educational institutions that are being created often set themselves the only priority tasks for the implementation of educational programs only. In our opinion, it is impossible to achieve effective management without taking into account and mutual integration of educational

and economic aspects of activity innovative educational institutions and the quality of educational services.

The approach to education mainly from the point of view of its social function creates a distorted picture of the place of educational structures in the economic system. Without denying the importance of the social function of education, we consider education as a factor of modern production. The content of the economics of education as a branch of scientific knowledge for several decades has been reduced to the rational use of financial resources allocated to educational institutions. In a centrally regulated economy, this approach was justified. In modern The view on the specifics of education as a factor of production is relevant in these conditions: as a resource, on the one hand, and a resource-consuming sphere, on the other. The purpose of this study is to study the management system of higher education. To achieve **the goal**, the following tasks should be **solved**:

- consideration of the historical stages of the development of the management system of higher education;
- analysis of the University's management system, taking into account the innovative strategic component.

The general methodological and theoretical foundations of management in education are considered in the works of S. Postovalov, V. Postovalov, M. Nikolaeva, Yu. V. Gromyko, Yu. S. Alferov, A. E. Potapov, A. I. Piskunov, etc. They consider a range of management problems that are fundamentally new and relevant for the practical reform of the educational system. These include new management values and goals, innovations in university management, methodology and technology for developing development programs, curricula and educational programs of various types of universities, social and legal protection of subjects of education, the activities of educational support services, certification of teaching staff, etc.

Kazakhstan's accession to the European educational space, ongoing socio-economic changes, and the development of the market of non-governmental higher professional educational institutions in the field of educational services have significantly complicated the conditions for the functioning of public sector universities. The competition has intensified. The problem of the management system of a competitive university is further aggravated due to the existing demographic decline, as a result of which there will be a decrease in demand for educational services [7]. Most recently, in the context of a planned In the administrative and command economy of Russia, all management functions in higher education institutions were performed by the state. The main task of the University's management system at that time was the rationalization of the management of the learning process and the implementation of orders and orders from higher authorities of the higher professional education system. The type of management system that was defined at that time in most Russian universities was related to managerial rationalism. This type of control is usually used to control closed systems, for which the weakest interaction with the external environment is the most characteristic. The change in the essence of socio-economic relations in society has led to a reduction in state budget financing of universities, the cessation of the existence of a centralized system of planning and distribution of young specialists. In that crisis period for the whole country, the conservative approach to the management methods used and inertia provided universities and the entire system of higher professional education with survival and a certain degree of stability. At the entrance to the XXI century, socio-economic transformations and Russia's openness to integration processes and innovative phenomena of the global economic, as well as the educational community, have formed a new external and internal

environment for the functioning of the higher professional education system Of Kazakhstan. Among the features of the functioning of the the kazakh higher education system at the present stage, the following factors can be identified:

- stabilization of the socio-economic situation with a tendency to increase the activity of industry; the change of working generations, which results in an increase in demand for personnel, especially highly qualified;

- the onset of the informatization stage, which is characterized by the transition of society and society as a whole from an industrial form of its development to a post-industrial or informational one, characterized by the intensification of communication links and information processing processes, the consequence of which is an increase in requirements for the quality of higher education;

- Ongoing reforms of the higher professional school of Kazakhstan, the main purpose of which is to develop the system of higher professional education in Kazakhstan and integrate it into an open pan-European educational space, which leads to the need to implement international principles of quality management of higher education, a system of certification and awarding academic degrees;

- the emergence of a large number of non-governmental organizations Universities that use the experience and best traditions of state universities and at the same time have high mobility due to their autonomy and independence, which results in the emergence of competition in the market for providing educational services.

- It is necessary to emphasize one more important feature: at the turn of the XX–XXI centuries, a new system of views on the management system appeared in the world, known in managerial and economic sciences as the "quiet managerial revolution", the essence of which lies in the integrated use of modern methods of management theory and information technology. At the same time, we are not talking about the destruction of existing structures, systems and management methods, but about their improvement in order to increase the efficiency and quality of functioning of socio-economic systems. These features of the situation in the country, the instability of the transitional economy, and the difficult financial and material situation of universities have made them open systems closely related to the external socio-economic environment and unstable market processes. In the modern theory of the management system, an approach to managing open systems in market relations characterized by instability of the external environment, including in a transitive economy, is known – a strategic approach, the methods of which are associated with setting the goals of the organization and with the maintenance of certain relationships with the environment, and allow the organization to achieve its goals in accordance with its internal capabilities and external conditions.

The introduction of strategic management methods at the University meets modern requirements caused by the peculiarities of the external environment, and should change the situation, orienting the University staff to improve methods of achieving set goals, increasing the efficiency of the University as a whole.

At the same time, it is necessary to use the whole range of modern approaches and methods of analysis and synthesis of socio-economic systems: historical approach, structural analysis, modern methods of management theory and information processing: methods of strategic analysis and planning, modeling of complex systems [9].

Thus, the specifics of the development of the socio-economic system of the country impose new quantitative and qualitative requirements on the activities of universities. The main problem

of state universities at the present stage is not only the lack of state budget financing, as is sometimes considered, but is of a deeper systemic nature and consists in the discrepancy between the methods and structures of the management system used in universities, inherited from the previous economic system, the urgent need to develop quantitatively and qualitatively, and It is to increase the economic effect of the University's activities and at the same time improve the quality of higher education. An additional difficulty in moving in this direction is the insufficient development of management methods in the field of education. It can be argued that so far the management system in universities remains an activity focused on intuition and experience, with weak information support and an obvious incompleteness of scientifically based management techniques.

Innovations are the main vector of development of the modern economy and today form the basis of the activities of not only high-tech and knowledge-intensive industries, including the education system, the level of which, along with the country's innovation system, is an indicator of its competitiveness in the world market. Focusing on innovation is the only way to respond to the high speed of change that organizations require constantly generating new "solution recipes". For organizations of higher professional education, this problem is the most urgent, since they are sources of personnel for a modern economy focused on an innovative path of development, who must possess competencies in the field of innovation management, in particular, the ability to create new knowledge. In order to fulfill their mission and remain competitive in the face of declining budget funding, universities They must have a high adaptive potential that allows them to develop in a changing environment. In this regard, the management system of an innovative university, which belongs to the open type of systems, should be formed taking into account the development of the innovative component at all levels of management [4].

The university as a system can be represented in the form of a model of the composition of the system (Fig.1), which reflects the subsystems of different levels. The scheme shown in the figure reflects the multilevel nature of the "University" system, which assumes many relationships between the subsystems of the university. O. G. Ilyina notes the complexity of interrelations in her work, considering the university as a system based on an organizational structure.

To date, there are several approaches to the formation of a university management system. Yu.S. Vasiliev V.V, M.P. Fedorov [3] distinguish four levels of management: operational solutions, strategic management tasks, tactical management tasks, operational management, which belong to a group of tasks. These levels intersect with functional areas of management.

E.N. Bogachev [6] proposes to identify two comprehensively targeted subsystems in the general management system of the University "capacity development", which is aimed at "developing and improving the technical base of the University, social development improvement of the system of economic relations", and "Management of the functioning of the University", the sphere includes the processes of "creation and sale of marketable products of types, effective use of resources, product quality.

O. G. Ilyin [6] considers the organizational structure of the university management from the point of view of strategic management and includes 11 control subsystems which are based on the following They have tasks ahead of them. The author includes "Planning of education", "Marketing of university activities", "Organization of training research work", "Advanced training and cooking", "Organization of teachers' work", "Hiring", "Staff development", "Remuneration", "Providing the basis for which several approaches to With Vasiliev, V.V. Glumanagement: the concept of tactical management, which relate to the time intersect with the functional ones,

distinguish two complex university management: "Management is aimed at the development and social development of on-farm enterprises from the university in the sphere of which marketable products of all product quality". the structure of the vision system of strategic subsystems, as a basis To the data of subsystems Marketing", "Finance", "Scientific qualifications and retraining of personnel".

The considered university management systems are complementary, but they do not provide for an innovative component as one of the elements, which, in our opinion, should be allocated to one of the management subsystems.

S.D. Reznik and V.M. Filippov consider the management system of a higher educational institution as a socio-economic system, which reflects the "interrelation of elements of the external environment, affecting the management system by a higher educational institution, and the final results of the activity of this system, achievable under the condition of effective use of the principles and mechanisms implementing the system of interrelations and relations between the object and the subject of management of this system" [10, p.45]. The authors refer to the subjects of management, that is, the management subsystem, educational management bodies, university management bodies, university management personnel. The managed subsystem includes several management subsystems: management of strategic development, management of academic work, management of scientific management of economic activity, management of external relations; management of social and educational work, management of administrative and economic activities. Scientists identify innovation management as a separate area of activity in the subsystem of strategic development management [5].

From our point of view, this approach is the most optimal and appropriate for the conditions of a modern economy focused on an innovative development path. However, the authors distinguish the strategic development management subsystem on the same level as the other subsystems, whereas the activities of the latter are determined by decisions taken at the strategic level. Based on the analysis of various approaches, we propose to consider the management system taking into account a specific strategic direction – innovation activity [2].

The proposed scheme reflects the relationship between strategic and tactical goals in the field of innovation, as well as the specifics of activities at each level of management. The subjects of external management of the university are the educational management bodies: the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, its subordinate organizations, and regional educational management bodies. At this level of management, the state policy and legal regulations governing educational, scientific and innovative activities in the field of education are being developed.

The University management system with accounting for innovation Activities Also, at the level of external management, the involvement of universities in federal and regional programs of scientific and innovative activities is being created through priority national projects and federal and regional target programs, which are implemented by the Ministry of Research and Science, the Federal Agency for Science and Innovation, and national education authorities [10].

The strategic management of the University is carried out by the Strategic development Committee, which includes members responsible for the development and implementation of the strategy. In the context of the development of innovative activity, strategic management, legal acts, Innovative activities in the field of education.

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Functional management is carried out by managers departments involved in the innovation process. At this level, strategic goals in the field of innovation are transformed into tactical goals of departments or responsibility centers.

The managed subsystem includes units that implement and/or ensure the innovation process, whose task is to implement the stages of the innovation process: idea generation – evaluation and selection of ideas – innovation development – innovation implementation – commercialization [1].

Thus, in the modern university management system The innovative component should be brought to the strategic level and reflected in all subsystems, which, in turn, is ensured by the choice of the appropriate organizational structure of the University, ensuring the consolidation of innovative goals for the relevant departments.

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